

A simple in-house-written program for examination of eligibility of the radiotherapy plans for the protocol prescriptions

Jeno Palvolgyi

Abstract. The radiotherapy plans should satisfy the protocol prescriptions. The RT plan eligibility is evaluated with radiotherapy protocols, including multiple prescriptions for the PTV and the organs at risk. The *dvhanal* in-house-written program allows the user to collect dose coverage data from the DVH file exported from the treatment planning system, and to examine the RT plan eligibility level for the protocol prescriptions.

Introduction

The RT plan quality assessment method developed by the Proknow Systems (proknowsystems.com) requires a RT structure file, a RT plan and a RT dose Dicom file, which solution is RT planning system independent.

At our institution, the Monaco 5.11 TPS is available, which does not export composite dose matrices, therefore, they cannot be evaluated with this method. The development aimed to create a program, which collects data from the DVH file exported from the TPS for single, multiple dose prescription RT plans, and for base plan+bias dose plan and the sum.

Materials and Methods

The *dvhanal* program was developed to evaluate RT plans prepared with the Monaco 5.11 treatment planning system (Elekta, Sweden) (TPS). The program runs under Windows 11, it was written in QB64, and a GUI in Python3.11. The **absolute volume** DVH file of the RT plan is exported from the TPS. The program also requires a protocol prescription files, which include the list of quantities to be collected, and also include the per-protocol and acceptable variation values, illustrated in Table 1. The protocol prescription files are created with Microsoft Excel spreadsheet program, and should be saved in CSV format with semicolon separation. The evaluation program (*dvh.exe*) splits the DVH.txt file into *dvh* files per-structures, performs the tasks stored in the protocol prescription file, and creates a *report.csv* file illustrated in Table 2.

protocol: Bladder 44+20Gy

				PP	PA
PTVpelvis	V	4400cGy	>	95	90%
PTVpelvis	D	0,03ccm	>	4840	5060cGy
PTVboost	V	6400cGy	>	95	90%
PTVboost	D	0,03ccm	>	6848	7360cGy
Rectum	V	3000cGy	<	50	55%
Rectum	V	5500cGy	<	10	15%
Rectum	V	7000cGy	<	15	15%
Femoral_Head_R	V	4500cGy	<	50	55%
Femoral_Head_R	D	0,03ccm	<	5000	5500cGy
Femoral_Head_L	V	4500cGy	<	50	55%
Femoral_Head_L	D	0,03ccm	<	5000	5500cGy
Bowel_Small	V	3000cGy	<	150	170ccm
Bowel_Small	V	4000cGy	<	30	35%
Bowel_Small	V	4500cGy	<	100	120ccm
Bowel_Small	V	5000cGy	<	15	20ccm
Bowel_Small	D	0,03ccm	<	5500	5700cGy

Table.1. Example of the Bladder cancer protocol prescription file tasks

column1: includes the Structure names, Column2. **V**: volume covered by dose included in column3. or **D**:dose of volume included in column3., Column6. includes the per-protocol (PP) value Column7. includes the acceptable variation (VA) value

Patient ID: 1~0101xxxxx

Plan Name: NewTmpl

protocol: Bladder
44+20Gy

				PP	PA		
PTVpelvis	V	4400cGy	>	95	90	97%	pp
PTVpelvis	D	0,03ccm	>	4840	5060	6166cGy	pp
PTVboost	V	6400cGy	>	95	90	98%	pp
PTVboost	D	0,03ccm	>	6848	7360	7166cGy	pp
Rectum	V	3000cGy	<	50	55	53%	va
Rectum	V	5500cGy	<	10	15	0%	pp
Rectum	V	7000cGy	<	15	15	0%	pp
Femoral_Head_R	V	4500cGy	<	50	55	0%	pp
Femoral_Head_R	D	0,03ccm	<	5000	5500	3051cGy	pp
Femoral_Head_L	V	4500cGy	<	50	55	0%	pp
Femoral_Head_L	D	0,03ccm	<	5000	5500	3048cGy	pp
Bowel_Small	V	3000cGy	<	150	170	17ccm	pp
Bowel_Small	V	4000cGy	<	30	35	0%	pp
Bowel_Small	V	4500cGy	<	100	120	1ccm	pp
Bowel_Small	V	5000cGy	<	15	20	0ccm	pp
Bowel_Small	D	0,03ccm	<	5500	5700	5172cGy	pp

Table 2. The report file includes the protocol prescriptions, and the evaluated values in Column 8. Column 10. includes the eligibility level: per-protocol (pp), or an acceptable variation (va), or an unacceptable variation (uv) remark.

With a GUI program (qui.exe), the user selects the exported DVH.txt file, and the protocol description file. They are copied into the \work folder. After running the dvh.exe evaluation program, the user loads the report.csv file into MS Excel.

Load dvh.txt: runs the file manager to select the DVH file exported from the TPS

Load protocol file: runs the file manager to select the protocol prescription file

Eval: runs the evaluation program

Load Report: runs a spreadsheet program for viewing the report file

run plotDVH: runs a graphic viewer program to show the relative DVH files with the pp, va, and maximal dose values

list Structure names: runs a spreadsheet program to list the exported structure names (struct.csv file) for debugging

Edit protocol file: runs a spreadsheet program to viewing and editing a protocol prescription file

Fig.1. The *dvhanal* program GUI

The relative volume dvh curves, the per-protocol values, and the acceptable variation, and the per protocol maximal values (D0,03ccm) are displayed with a graphic viewer illustrated in Fig.2.

Fig.2. Graphic view of the DVH curves with per-protocol values (filled circles), the acceptable variation values, and the D(0.03)ccm values stored in the protocol prescription file.

Discussion

With the *dvhanal* program, the user can evaluate single or multiple prescription plans, also the base plan+bias dose plan per sub-plans and the composite one with the corresponding protocol prescription files. The program makes possible to compare the dose coverage of structures with different treatment modalities, or to evaluate the patients' RT plans with different protocols [1]. The reason of necessity of exporting absolute volume DVH file, instead of the relative one is: some protocols require not only a percentage, but also an absolute value volume prescription for some OARs. and the absolute volume DVH export file includes this data.

There are some restrictions:

1. Since the DVH export file structure is TPS specific, the *dvhanal* program works with the Monaco TPS DVH.txt export file only.
2. In the protocol description file is: the tasks should prescribe absolute dose values in cGy.
3. Since the DVH export file is quite large, it is advised to select for export in the TPS the necessary structure data only.
4. The program is not designed to evaluate stereotactic treatments.
5. The program should be installed into the folder: c:\dvhanal\work, while the protocol prescription files in c:\dvhanal\protocols, otherwise some modifications in QUI program is needed.

Disclaimer. The program comes without any warranty, has not been approved for clinical use by any regulatory bodies. Use at own risk.

Reference

- [1] Palvolgyi, J. (2025) Comparison of the Organs at Risk's doses in Pelvic Radiotherapy. Zenodo <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15028640>